

WFloT Conference

“Use of High-Precision GNSS Receivers in Precision Farming Applications”

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RFSAT Limited (2)

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AgriBIT Project - Strategic Objectives

Data Space solutions

- Higher precision location services
- Affordable, European source, high precision Galileo and EGNOS GNSS receiver
- Bundle of PA services for farmers and farm advisors
- Strategy for services uptake from farm advisors and farmers
- Open service-oriented platform architecture to enable the integration of intelligent analytics and more services by third parties /providers

AgriBIT Results

AgriBIT improves agriculture chain :

- **optimised usage of resources** ranging from fertilizers and pesticides to water
- **increased crops diversity** across smaller areas of land
- **extended availability of Precision Agriculture (PA) services** even in **challenging conditions**

high cloud coverage, when AgriBIT makes use of multispectral satellite observation capabilities offered by Landsat 8, Crop Monitoring service from EOS or CropSAT service from Datavaxt.

AgriBIT offers a range of :

- **operational services**
 - 3 GNSS-enabler services
 - 8 GNSS-enabled services
- EU-sourced **economic high-precision GNSS receiver**
- **collaborative services** that cover the **complete value chain of precision agriculture**, from monitoring to application and precise and automated machinery guidance.

AgriBIT Consortium

8 partners

1 Large company

1 Research organization

4 SME

3 End Users

AgriBIT Pilot – Greece Peach Orchards

Context

The pilot test case in Greece, will take place in Pella Municipality, Central Macedonia Prefecture and with Agricultural Cooperative of Pella (ACP) as piloting user.

Pilot focus

AgriBIT’s pilot will therefore focus on GNSS technologies able to work even in “GPS-unfriendly” environments like orchard fields. A GNSS system that can work seamlessly, able to retrieve data from on-the-go sensors and UGV’s, and provide advices for managing their production, will help them improving their yields and increasing their products quality.

KPI	Current	With AgriBIT	Verification Means
High precision GNSS positioning under tree canopy	As density of the tree canopy increases, geodetic receivers struggle to obtain the highest accuracy phase fixed centimetre level solution	100%	Use of UAS and UGV for crop scouting
Availability of precision agriculture services for orchard cultivations	No	Yes	All AgriBIT services validated in orchard crops

AgriBIT Pilot – Portugal / tomato disease advance alerts

Context

CCTI operates a tomato field plantation located in the Lezíria do Ribatejo, Portugal. Tomato monocultures are attacked by diseases and pests; in 2018, the diseases included mildew, bacterial spots, mites and tuta absoluta (pests). The list of diseases changes and spread very fast during the crop growth period.

Pilot focus

AgriBIT solution combines EO data from Sentinel-2 MSI to identify crop problems which could be solved after the harvest period and UAVs with multi-spectral cameras to solve problems during crop growth and productive period. This piloting case therefore fully implements the multi-layered model proposed by AgriBIT and is key in demonstrating the added value across the full chain of activities.

KPI	Current	With AgriBIT	Verification Means
Identification of pest or disease at growing time	Naked eye	Non-intrusive Early detection	Detection of pest or disease
Identification of unhealthy plants during crop grow and fruitful period	Naked Eye	Non-intrusive Early detection	Detection of unhealthy plants
Correct delivery of correction measures	Applied to whole field	Application only to affected areas	Amount of chemicals or energy applied and its effectiveness

AgriBIT Pilots – Italy - Precision vineyard

Context

Pilot on grapevine (*Vitis vinifera* L.) is conducted in high-plant-density vineyards, in Umbria for production of high quality red and white wine. Vineyards extends over 200 ha with plants warping of 0.9 m x 2 m (5550 plants / ha).

Piloting focus

Starting from Sentinel-2 MSI (already in use from Agriculus System) this pilot tests:

- acquisition of multispectral data with UAVs to calculate vegetation maps and correlation with spatial yield data based on multispectral imagery and with integration of satellite data
- Automated machinery guidance: the collection of machinery data georeferenced with the high-precision GNSS receiver compliant with Galileo and EGNOS to spatially identify all the farming activities.

KPI	Current	With AgriBIT	Verification Means
Identification of optimal harvest period	manual sampling and lab analysis	improve spatial resolution, more frequent updates, reduce labour costs	comparison of estimated yield indicators with measured ones
Identification of phenological phase	direct observation in vineyard by trained technician	improve spatial resolution, more frequent updates, reduce time consuming labour	comparison of estimated phenological phase with the observed ones
Precision Irrigation	No	Improve spatial resolution, remote control of water stress in vineyard	AgriBIT services validated in vineyard

AgriBIT Architecture

- **Synergies between** Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) and Earth Observation (EO),
- **Combination of GNSS and EO** information with 1) on-field and on-machine sensors and actuators, and 2) expert agricultural knowledge to deliver simple, high precision and continuously available services.
- **Exploitation of satellite information and data** from the field with Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies aiming to deliver performing data-driven services.
- **Automated detection and classification** of any issue faced in the field from surveillance images (e.g. Machine Vision technology).
- **Automated monitoring** and machine operations in the field, as well as provision of **Decision Support** based on previous experiences automatically analysed by Machine Learning (ML) algorithms.

Architecture

Physical layer

Services layer

Data and Applications layer

Innovative Building Blocks

Crop Growth Monitoring

This service will deliver a number of Earth Observation (EO) derived vegetation indices calculated from satellite multispectral data. Crop Growth Monitoring service provides an overview of **plant vigor** across the field. can be used to:

- To identify locations of abiotic or biotic **stress**
- to investigate the cause before significant yield **damage** is sustained.
- to analyze **performance** overtime, with a spatial overlay of results obtained from specific varieties of crops under the varied conditions of the season,
- The resource accepts a JSON object containing the following properties: geometry (geojson) date (string)
- The output is a map of the indexes

Crop Growth Monitoring - indexes

- OSAVI (Optimized Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index): OSAVI tracks crop development dynamics since it measures photosynthetically active biomass in plants and maps variability in canopy density. This index is best used in areas with relatively sparse vegetation where soil is visible through the canopy.
- CRI1 (Carotenoid Reflectance Index): Carotenoids function in light absorption processes in plants, as well as in protecting plants from the harmful effects of too much light. Weakening vegetation contains higher concentrations of carotenoids, so this index is one measure of stressed vegetation.
- ARI (Anthocyanin Reflectance Index): Anthocyanins are water-soluble pigments abundant in newly forming leaves and those undergoing senescence. Weakening vegetation contains higher concentrations of anthocyanins, so this index is one measure of stressed vegetation.

Irrigation Scheduling

- It is based on daily calculation of crop **evapotranspiration** at parcel level.
- In the case of arable crops, the service is a result of the combined use of agro-meteorological data (observed and **forecasted** for the proximal seven days) and high-spatial resolution (10x10 m) **multispectral satellite images**
- In the case of perennial crops only meteorological data are used for the calculation of the reference evapotranspiration, whereas the crop coefficient is constant per month.

Crop Yield Estimation

- To predict crop yield AgriBIT leverage AquaCrop
- AquaCrop is a crop water productivity model developed by the Land and Water Division of FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization) in 2009
- It requires a number of data in terms of crop and soil characteristics, climate, farm management practices, initial soil moisture conditions
- The results of the yield (12 in total) represent the effect of the future climate on the potential yield.
- The 12 yield values are derived by applying certain climatic scenarios (Representative Concentration Pathways - RCPs).
- Scenario includes temperature changes, greenhouse emissions , and so on
- These scenarios have a multitude of ensembles (sub-scenarios), differing in the initial forcing conditions.

Tillage scheduling

This service calculates the optimum and the range of soil water content for tillage. Based on the soil moisture (water content) a decision is provided. The aim of the service is to provide a range of conditions under which tillage operations can be performed without damage to the soil structure as would occur if the soil is too wet, and without excessive use of energy as would occur if the soil is too dry.

Results include:

- **Gravimetric_soil_moisture map:** presented with a heatmap according to the values of the pixels
- **Decision map:** an heatmap with different colors for different decisions. The decisions are medium, bad, optimum, good and should be provided in a legend.

Pest and disease early warning

- AgriBIT employs and apply predictive models to warn for possible pest generation emergence, as well as for the possible contamination of the crops by fungal diseases.
- Current weather conditions and 6-day weather forecast from AgroApps Weather Intelligence Engine will be fed into the system as the meteorological input of the models. The prediction will take into account the high-risk, susceptible, vegetation stages during the crop growing season.

GNSS high precision system

- Incorporated RTK GNSS module from u-Blox, several PCB boards have been built to test different scenarios, e.g. Wi-Fi and cellular networking coverage and stand alone functions.
- Small-size considering early prototype 3 x 4 x 5 cm (125g, thus suitable for UAVs)
- **Power delivery is very important and few options have been deployed and provisioned, such as battery power, 12/24V vehicle onboard power and back-up solar panels.**
- **Tests that were carried out in open sky and within city areas, successfully demonstrated compliance with required specs.**
- Optional LAN module with RJ45 connector e.g. when wireless RTCM stream is not **essential**
- Optional module for obtaining speed and direction of the vehicle from the CAN bus for the Dead Reckoning capability has been tested and demonstrated to work.

Plans for further evolution:

- Reduce size by up to 50%
- **New, more robust casing**
- Improve performance in RTK mode in varying network performance

High-precision GNSS receiver prototype

12AOK RTK receiver, specifications vs actual performance delivered

		Requirement	Performance delivered
1	Satellite constellations supported	Galileo (obligatory), GPS (essential), Glonass/BeiDou/AZSS/IRNSS (optional)	GPS, Galileo, BeiDou, Glonass, QZSS
2	Accuracy (autonomous)	<1m ± 25% (static test conditions – validation test) and <2m (dynamic conditions)	OK
3	Accuracy (RTK corrections)	<1cm ± 25% (static test conditions – validation test) and <2.5cm (dynamic conditions)	=>1cm static, =>2cm dynamic
4	RTK corrections will be most likely	EURIF-IP and/or Metrica in RTCM 2.x/3.x (messages TBC: provisionally 1, 2, 3 and 9)	OK, any RTCM correction service
5	Accuracy (SBAS)	<30cm ± 25% (static test conditions– validation test) and <60cm (dynamic conditions)	OK
6	SBAS support	EGNOS (obligatory), WAAS/GAGAN/SouthPAN/KAAS/MSAS (optional)	EGNOS, WAAS, GAGAN, MSAS, SDCM
7	TTF	preferably <30sec and not more than 60sec (cold start), 1sec (reacquisition)	OK
8	Update frequency	1, 5, 10, 20 Hz	OK, up to 30Hz
9	Datum	WGS-84 (essential), other TBC (optional)	OK
10	Antenna connector	SMA-F	OK, SMA and uFL
11	I/F for output position	Bluetooth (essential) and USB/Serial (optional)	OK
12	Output protocol	NMEA-0183 (essential), other (optional)	OK
13	IP connectivity for RTK corrections	Wi-Fi (e.g. use Wi-Fi Access Point or smartphone as a modem via Wi-Fi Direct) and/or embedded Mobile Broadband (optional)	OK, and LAN (RJ45) and LoRa
14	Durability	standard outdoor (IP67 for temperature, splash/dust-proof, no immersion required)	OK
15	OS supported for application	Android and MS Windows 10/11, iOS (not planned)	Android and Windows
16	Power supply	5V DC via USB-C (preferable) or 12V DC (option), current <1A (preferable)	OK, 5 - 15V DC, < 1A
17	Power consumption	might be important for e.g. use on UGV (in the project) and/or future	Depends on update frequency
18	Device configuration	via Android or Windows application connected via Bluetooth or USB	OK, any device running web browser
19	Target form factor	12/8/4cm (preferable) though the prototype could be a bit larger	OK
20	Target weight	<400g (commercial version), <750g (prototype)	OK
21	Target price	<£430 (commercial price?) + up to 50% (offset for prototype version)	OK with patch multiband antenna
22	Max altitude	20.000m	OK up to 80.000m
23	Max speed	500m/s	OK
24	USB power	5V	OK, discussed in 16. Power supply
25	Battery power	Li-Ion with 10-12hrs autonomy (in the worst case we might use a standard power bank)	6Hrs with Li-Ion 3.7V, 4500mAh, 5Hz

Multispectral images using UAV/UAS

Drone: DJI Mavic 3M (Multispectral0, containing:

- Near-infrared NIR camera
- Red (R) 650nm \pm 16nm
- Red-edge (RE) 730nm \pm 16nm
- Green (G) 560nm \pm 16nm
- RGB 20MPixel

Sunlight sensor: sunlight sensor captures solar irradiance and records it in an image file, allowing for light compensation of image data during 2D reconstruction. This results in more accurate NDVI results, as well as improved accuracy and consistency of data acquired over time.

Generic MVP for Cloud Applications

Fast System Solution for Sensor → Cloud applications

Hypothetical spatial-temporal distribution

Hypothetical distributions

Single source

Multiple source

NO wind

WITH wind

Real-life distribution of humidity in Valencia

Real-life distribution of PM₁₀ in Hamburg

NO₂ emission distribution in Rome

distribution of SO₂ in Bratislava

Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service

RFSAT offers operational service sending data to THIS (INGV) from CAMS:

- Processes ALL available real-time atmospheric quality parameters (60)
- Processes currently NetCDF files (optionally GRIG v1 & v2)
- World/European overlay maps generated as KMZ files

Usefulness of indexes and reflectance maps

Reflectance maps hold key radiometric information which is combined to generate the index maps (illustration below) that have become a tool for more efficient, less diseased, and better yielding crops.

NDVI maps are widely used in agriculture, forestry, and ecology to monitor the growth and health of vegetation and to identify areas of stress or damage. NDVI values can also be used to map and classify vegetation types, and to detect changes in vegetation cover over time.

Benefit of high-precision GNSS receivers

NDVI index map with NIR reflectance

2065 images collected (all cameras)

Colour codes areas identify:

- **Red:** human built environment
- **Yellow:** dry ground
- **Green:** healthy olive trees

High-precision GNSS receiver (1.5cm) enabled:

- Precisely geo-reference index maps
- 3D-model field at GSD = $\sim 0.5\text{cm}/\text{pixel}$
- Precise volumetric analysis of crop growth

Drone flight #1 in Greece 20-April-2023

The 3D mesh has been produced from 1975 images to assess crop growth from its 3D shape.

GSD: 0.92cm/pixel

Example NDVI index shows low level of soil moisture (red), as well as good health of olive trees (green).

Other indexes are also available: [Green](#), [Red](#), [Red-edge](#), [NIR](#), RGB ([red](#), [green](#), [blue](#)).

Volume 1	
Terrain 3D Area:	15670.84 m ²
Cut Volume:	6950.38 ± 219.51 m ³
Fill Volume:	-0.06 ± 0.04 m ³
Total Volume:	6950.32 ± 219.55 m ³

Drone flight #2 in Greece 22-May-2023

3D mesh was produced from 1135 images to assess crop growth from its envelope.

GSD: 0.92cm/pixel

Time: 26min

Distance: 1.72km

Area: 14,757m²

Example NDVI index shows low level of soil moisture (red), as well as good health of olive trees (green).

Other indexes are also available:

- [Green](#), [Red](#), [Red-edge](#), [NIR](#),
- RGB ([red](#), [green](#), [blue](#)).

Pest/Bacterial detection using AI

RFSAT develops online application running under Matlab Application Server to process images from e.g. drones and detect cases of (for now) tomato leaf miner (*Tuta absoluta*). Model uses Squeeze Net CNN with public datasets to reach accuracy of 93%. Severity/density analysis rules are under development.

AgriBIT Pests & Bacterial Infections (H2020-AgriBIT)

Buttons: Load Image to Analyse, Help

Left image: Original photo of a tomato plant with damage.

Middle image: Heatmap overlay on the photo showing areas of high detection probability (red/yellow).

Right image: Histogram of severity scores.

Severity	Density
0	~0.17
0.25	1.00
0.5	~0.17
0.75	~0.03
1	~0.03

Density: minimal (17%)
Severity: low (82%)

AgriBIT

Sign In

Home Join

Welcome to the AGRIBIT Community Platform

<h3>Precision Agriculture Services</h3> <p>Access the platform to explore AgriBIT's services. AgriBIT Develop EO-based PA services for farmers and agricultural consultants, through the combined use of EO data from Copernicus and UAVs, GNSS and ground sensors provide 8 smart PA services.</p> <p>Visit</p>		
<h3>Big Data Analytics APIs</h3> <p>A Machine 2 Machine support is available through the Allida platform in order to take advanced and integrate the application and workflow create. APIs are available by the community platform.</p> <p>Visit</p>		

The screenshot shows the AgriBIT web application dashboard. The interface includes a top navigation bar with the AgriBIT logo and user information (View: ACPella, rfsat). A left sidebar contains menu items: Dashboard, WORK (Activities), EXECUTE (Analysis, Observe), and EQUIPMENT (Parcels, Data Sources). The main content area features several sections:

- Next 7 days parcels in warning:** A section with a warning icon and the text "No data available".
- Last Updated Parcels:** A section with a plus icon and a "Show all" button. It displays three parcel cards, each with a map thumbnail and details:
 - (335) ANDROS - 365-512-5847-0X, acp@agribit.eu, 31/1/23
 - (334) LUTSIANA PLATYMOON - 3, acp@agribit.eu, 31/1/23
 - (277) CATHERINA A37 - 362-513-, acp@agribit.eu, 31/1/23
- Parcels Map:** A map view showing the geographical location of the parcels.
- Last Updated Activities:** A section with a plus icon and a "Show all" button. It includes a "Last Year Activities" sub-section with "No data available".

At the bottom, a footer contains the text: "This project has received funding from the European Union Agency for the Space Programme under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004259 Version: 2.4.1".

(272) TRAIANOS TERZIS - 364-513-3180-204

No parcel place

User: app@agribit.eu | **Organization:** ACPella | **Last Update:** 31/1/23

Crop List

Name	Type	Season (year)	Periodicity (weeks)	Sowing Date	Status
TRAIANOS TERZIS	peach	2023	0	2018/11/5	current

Activity List

Info Detail	Show on Map	Type	Last Update	Description
No warnings				

Pest and Disease Early Warning

No warnings

This project has received funding from the European Union under the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101094259 - version 1.4.1

The screenshot shows the AgriBIT web application interface. The browser address bar displays the URL: localhost:4200/#/parcels/6387355abacb112044a5bd86. The application header includes the AgriBIT logo, a navigation menu icon, and a user profile section for 'agribit'. The main content area is titled 'Home / Parcels / Parcel Detail' and displays the following information:

grapevine	grapevine	2023	0	2022/10/10	current
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Below this is an 'Activity List' section with a table containing three rows of activity data:

Info Detail	Show on Map	Type	Last Update	Description
[i]	[m]	Tree	28/1/21	no
[i]	[m]	Sample	28/1/21	si
[i]	[m]	Tree	22/2/21	

At the bottom of the activity list, there is a chart showing the progression of three types of diseases over time from 2023-05-13 00:00 to 2023-05-19 00:00. The legend indicates: powdery-mildew (black line), downy-mildew (teal line), and botrytis-grey-mould (yellow line).

Date	powdery-mildew	downy-mildew	botrytis-grey-mould
2023-05-13 00:00	2	1	3
2023-05-14 00:00	2	1	3
2023-05-15 00:00	1	2	3
2023-05-16 00:00	1	1	3
2023-05-17 00:00	1	1	3
2023-05-18 00:00	1	1	3
2023-05-19 00:00	1	1	3

The footer of the application contains the text: 'This project has received funding from the European Union Agency for the Space Programme under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004259'.

The screenshot displays the AgriBIT web application interface. The browser address bar shows the URL: <https://agribit-be.eng.it/gui/#/analysis/parcels-yieldestimation/64edfc38d4cdf332f475dabe>. The application header includes the AgriBIT logo, a navigation menu, and user information (View: agricolus, rfsat).

The main content area is titled "Yield Estimation" and includes a "Delete" button and a "Go Back" button. Key information displayed includes:

- Last Update:** 29/8/23
- Start Date:** 2024-03-01
- End Date:** 2030-09-01
- Status:** complete
- Message:** Simulation completed

The "Parcel" section identifies the location as "(230) Sangiovese 35 - Sangiovese 35". Below this is a map showing the parcel location. A legend below the map lists scenarios: rcp26, rcp45, rcp85, r121p1, r111p1, r21p1, and r31p1. A line graph shows yield estimation data over time from 2024-09-27 to 2029-09-27. The graph shows a steady increase in yield for all scenarios over the period.

At the bottom of the interface, a footer states: "This project has received funding from the European Union Agency for the Space Programme under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004259. Version 2.4.1".

Conclusions

- The AgriBIT project will conclude in June 2024
- The high precision Galileo / EGNOS GNSS receiver has been finalized and validated
- PA services for farmers and farm advisors are still under development
- Several piloting tests are still ahead in Q2/2024 and Q3/2024 (extension)
- Three (3) more UAV flights are to be done for comparative purposes
- Working on a marketing strategy for service uptake to farm advisors and farmers
- Ongoing work on service-oriented platform integration with support to 3rd-parties for integration of AgriBIT intelligent analytics and other services

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Thank you for Your attention

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